

D7.2 - Report on service integration

Lead Partner:	KIT
Version:	V1.1
Status:	submitted
Dissemination Level:	PU
Document Link:	10.5281/zenodo.7625864

Deliverable Abstract

This document describes the work done in T7.2 which is to support the community pilots from WP6, with their uptake of the available EOOSC-Pillar resources/services and implementation of the (prototypical) science demonstrators. In parallel T7.2 coordinated for several services and resources: a) the integration with the Indigo-IAM, one of the federated EOOSC-AAI solutions of the EOOSC core implementation and b) the onboarding into EOOSC catalogue and Marketplace. Thus, enabling access to distributed applications and resources in EOOSC for the scientific services provided in EOOSC-Pillar.

COPYRIGHT NOTICE

This work by Parties of the EOSC-Pillar is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). The EOSC-Pillar project is co-funded by the European Union Horizon 2020 programme under grant number 857650.

DELIVERY SLIP

<i>Date</i>	<i>Name</i>	<i>Partner/Activity</i>	<i>Date</i>
From:	Lisana Berberi	KIT	June 2022
Moderated by:			
Reviewed by:			
Approved by:			

DOCUMENT LOG

<i>Issue</i>	<i>Date</i>	<i>Comment</i>	<i>Author/Contributors</i>
v0.1	15.02.2022	Writing table of contents	Lisana Berberi (KIT)
v0.2	03.03.2022	GPU as a service completed FG-iRODS completed	Geneviève Romier (CNRS) Jérôme Pansanel (CNRS)
v0.3	19.03.2022	Add requirements elicitation process	Lisana Berberi (KIT)
v0.4	23.03.2022	Add information on support given to onboarding to EOSC catalogue ready-to-use services	Luciano Gaido (INFN)
v0.5	05.04.2022	Add community requirements from each thematic service; add technical ones	Lisana Berberi (KIT) Yannis Govinda (CNRS)
v0.6	14.04.2022	Add info on Laniakea, Galaxy-E D4Science VRE, AstroODA, thematic service; Add info on Readmetrics service	Lisana Berberi (KIT) Beatrice Chiavarini (Cineca) Pietro Mandreoli (CNR-IBIOM) Claudio Pisa (GARR) Yvan Le Bras (MNH) Leonardo Candella (CNR) Volodymyr Savchenko (UniGE) Thomas Porquet (Couperin)
v0.7	28.04.2022	Add info on Pico2 service	Jean-Marc Frigerio (INRAE)
v0.8	29.04.2022	Add info on Oyster, Marketplace services	Pablo de Andres (Fraunhofer) Yoav Nahshon (Fraunhofer) Jos van Wezel (KIT)

V0.9	04.05.2022	Add info on section 4(EOSC AAI) Summarized the list of services	Lisana Berberi (KIT) Enrico Vianello (INFN) Olivier Rouchon(CINES)
V1.0	16.05.2022	Add a short description of the requirement elicitation process diagram; Fix formatting, layout, cross and biblio references	Lisana Berberi (KIT)
V1.1	23.06.2022	Addressing reviewers' comments	Lisana Berberi (KIT) Rob Carillo (Trust-IT) Dirk Helm (Fraunhofer)

TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

Terminology/Acronym	Definition
SP	Service Provider
iRODS	Integrated Rule-Oriented Data System
F2DS	Federated Fair Data Space is a metadata repository
AAI	Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
F2F	Face-face meeting

Contents

1.	Introduction	6
2.	Support the implementation of demonstrators to achieve the community scientific goal	7
2.1	Requirement elicitation process.....	8
2.2	Requirements analysis results	11
2.2.1	List of community requirements per each demonstrator	11
2.2.2	List of the derived technical requirements.....	17
3.	EOSC-Pillar Available Resources/Services	20
3.1	Summary of the services	20
3.2	Laniakea-Galaxy	22
3.2.1	Galaxy-E for Ecology Initiative.....	24
3.3	GPU container as a Service	26
3.4	VRE/VLab using D4Science technology	27
3.5	FG-iRODS	29
3.6	Pico2	30
3.7	OYSTER and MarketPlace	31
3.8	ReadMetrics.....	33
3.9	MMODA	34
4.	Support on integration with the EOSC-core services	36
5.	Support on integration with the onboarding process to EOSC catalogue/marketplace	39
6.	Conclusions.....	41
7.	References.....	42
8.	Appendix-1.....	43
9.	Appendix-2.....	44
10.	Appendix-3.....	47

Executive summary

This document serves as a confirmation of the activities performed in T7.2 Support for the integration of national services.

This report discusses how the requirement gathering process and results out of it are conducted and the support activities provided to the service providers to meet the criteria of being part of EOSC catalogue and Marketplace.

We conducted a gap analysis to check and track which of the requirements could not be met. In case a requirement could not be met, then a gap (i.e., a missing functionality/feature of a service) arises. No gaps resulted from the gap analysis we performed, with the exception of some requirements still being resolved.

A twofold support was given: a) integration with the AAI instance and b) integration to onboard the service into the EOSC catalogue and Marketplace.

1. Introduction

This document reports on the support provided to all the services (either thematic, common or data repository) offered from different partners in the EOSC-Pillar project to be integrated with so-called EOSC federating core services or to be/are onboarded into EOSC Marketplace¹.

Among the list, we selected and prioritised those services that have not been previously in the EOSC Portal or Marketplace and which received an explicit service demand from a specific Use Case (UC) from WP6: “EOSC in action: Use cases and Community driven pilots” (extracted from a template filled out during the first 6 months of the project).

To accomplish this, we followed the procedure and the guidelines available from Deliverable 7.1 Guidelines and Recommendations for the Technical Integration of Resources and Services into the EOSC (Gaido, et al., 2021) on how to integrate these regional services to EOSC.

First, we designed/set-up a process for requirements gathering (see section 2.1) where we identified the needs of the stakeholders from the WP6 use cases associated with a specific user story in order to achieve the community’s scientific goals. These thematic service needs were translated into so-called “community pilots requirements” that are uniquely identified and aligned with a short description.

Second, we showed/provided a tabular list of the technical requirements that have been derived in order to address the community pilots requirements from the analysis results we conducted (see section 2.2), where we tracked which resource/service or third party this requirement is dependent to, and its status.

Finally, we conducted a gap analysis to check and track which of the requirements could not be met. In case a requirement could not be met, then a gap (i.e., a missing functionality/feature of a service) arises. No gaps resulted from the gap analysis we performed, with the exception of some requirements that are still being resolved. Moreover, we report on two other supporting activities we work: a) the support we provide to service providers in EOSC-Pillar to integrate their service with the Indigo-IAM service as one of the federated EOSC-AAI core services for seamless access to distributed resources (see section 4); b) the support on the onboarding process to EOSC catalogue and Marketplace (see section 5).

We show a list of the EOSC-Pillar service portfolio with all the resources/services from existing partners in Section 3.1 summarised by main attributes such as: availability, TRL, AAI interface etc.

Then, a short description with some information on relevant architecture and deployments are presented from subsections 3.2 to 3.9 . A detailed information on these services will be published in the next deliverable of T7.4 (D7.4).

¹ <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/>

2. Support the implementation of demonstrators to achieve the community scientific goal

T7.2 starts the process to gather technical requirements when a new request from a user community is identified. We used a top-down approach starting from the high-level requirements identified as user stories (US), the sub-use cases (changed the original term use case, not to confuse with the use case as community-driven pilots from WP6) associated with each US are defined and linked to the technical requirements that derive from them. We compiled the collected information for each analysed demonstrator named “Community Pilot Requirements dB” as listed in separated tables in the following subsection. To give more context, in the following page, we will briefly review the three aforementioned pieces of information that, once extracted, help to identify the expected objectives and outcomes of the different stakeholders involved (i.e., customers and development teams) and facilitate the communication among them.

User stories are informal, natural language description of one or more features of a software system.

They can be characterized by:

- Description of the benefit and value to the user.
- Outline, in a non-technical language, of the desired outcome of a customer’s or user’s end goal.

User stories might take the following forms:

- "As a <role>, I want <capability> so that <receive benefit>"
- "In order to <receive benefit> as a <role>, I want <goal/desire>"
- "As <persona>, I want <what?> so that <why?>" where a persona is a fictional stakeholder (e.g., user). A persona may include a name, picture; characteristics, behaviours, attitudes, and a goal which the product should help them achieve.

An example of an extracted user story is: “As a researcher, I would like to access a subset of genomics data from a given cohort in order to perform analysis/computation on these data without having to transfer them”.

Sub-Use cases are action lists or event steps typically defining the interactions between a role/actor and a system to achieve a goal. They describe the visible behaviour of a system from the user’s point of view.

They:

- Describe the interaction between the actor and a system.
- Refer to the list of actions, derived from the user stories, between a role or actor and a system to achieve the goal (where ‘actor’ can be people or other systems).

- The dependencies with EOSC-Pillar available services for each action are already identified at this stage.

A single sub-use case gets its name from the goal the actor wants to achieve and is a series of actions performed in a defined order.

A simple example of a sub-use case is the following: “1) have access to a data repository; 2) find satellite data; 3) format data; 4) perform analysis using notebook on demand on data of interest from remote facilities

Technical requirements describe the technical work that needs to be implemented on the EOSC-Pillar services to enable the sub-use cases.

- Technical requirements are the small units of development or integration work to be done by the technical groups and product/provider teams within WP5 and WP7.
- A new technical requirement is first recorded in a spreadsheet format.
- Each requirement contains the following information:

- Formal description
- Source sub-use case
- The dependent resource/service
- Status (done, in progress, To-do)
- Gap (if requirement is not satisfied)
- Resolved (gap is closed).

Technical support people from T7.4 Ready to use services assess these new community requirements and they take actions accordingly on how to implement them following an internal procedure by investigating the relevant solutions. They try to satisfy each requirement and acting as a bridge between the customer and the product teams.

2.1 Requirement elicitation process

In order to adequately capture the requirements coming from scientific communities in WP6 we designed a process model as depicted in the diagram in Fig. 1 using BPMN notation² as a de-facto standard for business processes diagrams.

We model this diagram as an orchestration between three different participants (i.e., “T7.2 & 7.3 reqs advisory” as a support team, “Community pilots [WP6]” and Service provider tech and dev team) represented graphically in three lanes in the single pool (depicted as a rectangular container) named “EOSC-Pillar requirements gathering Unit” to organise and categorise activities according to function or role and the interactions between the parties involved. This process starts with activity (represented with a rectangular box) “Extract high-level requirements” being executed by the team of T7.2 and 7.3. A preliminary list of these requirements is prepared by the community’s team in WP6 (named as stakeholders) in order to implement their

² <https://www.omg.org/spec/BPMN/2.0/>

use case implementation. After stakeholders agreed, this list is revised by adding the required details. Then, the requirements should be prioritised and stored in a specific database (represented with a datastore, i.e., disk).

The flow shifts to the technical and/or development team of a service provider to assess the requirements for correctness. If it's correct then they investigate/design (represented with rectangular box with "+" sign) the relevant solutions to address it, otherwise more details to be issued are asked from the WP6 team.

If the technical team internally manage to fulfil the requirement(s) then they update the relevant information on the database, otherwise they raise a gap and then try to resolve it. In our case there were no gaps to be resolved. The process ends when stakeholders are notified about the fulfilment of the requirements they issued.

The results of this gathering process we conducted are described in the subsections below.

Fig. 1 Requirement gathering process diagram

2.2 Requirements analysis results

We output the results from our requirement analysis process in two different subsections, sub section 2.2.1 describes all the requirements collected from each demonstrator in WP6 whereas subsection 2.2.2 describes the technical requirements that were derived from the community requirements.

2.2.1 List of community requirements per each demonstrator

We received an explicit service demand from four out of nine different science related demonstrators proposed in WP6 to utilise services/resources from our service portfolio. The rest make use of their own resources.

First, we give a short description of the demonstrators to understand what is the prototype they want to build, the target community and the main objective and achievement. We extracted information from existing deliverable of D6.2 “Demonstrators and success stories from the use cases” (Rizzo, et al. 2022).

Secondly, in the following tables we list the requirements for each demonstrator(prototype) implementation as sample sub-use cases.

Demonstrator #6.6 - Exploring reference Data through existing computing services for the bioinformatics

Objective: Galaxy is one of the prevailing workflow management systems for bioinformatics, aiming to make computational biology accessible to research scientists that do not have computer programming or systems administration experience. How can scientists connect this powerful tool seamlessly with many data sources? How can they do so in a coherent way using different instances of Galaxy? Can they run it locally or on a secured infrastructure that handles patient data? Can they compare the results of those different scenarios? Those are the main questions this use-case wants to address.

Target users: The demonstrator targets the Bioinformatics community, and especially that of the ELIXIR ESFRI³.

Sub use-case#	Title	Dependency on other resource/services	Status	Demonstrator#	User stories	User story#
SUC 1	Access a Dataverse instance to publish datasets produced by researchers working in a specific life science institute	INRAE dedicated VMs for Dataverse SW, database and solr	Done	#6.6	As a researcher, I would like to access a subset of genomics data from a given cohort in order to perform analysis/computation on these data without having to transfer them.	US1
SUC 2	Format data correctly using the commonly used standards	INRAE VMs, Inserm prototype repo	Done	#6.6	As a bioinformatician (Galaxy user) I would like to know how to format my data in order to ensure it can be used properly throughout my workflows	US2

³ <https://elixir-europe.org/collaborations/esfri>

SUC 3	Retrieve data of interests by executing API calls	Laniakea-Galaxy, F2DS prototype API methods and issues	in progress	#6.6	As a researcher, I would like to access a subset of genomics data from a given cohort in order to perform analysis/computation on these data without having to transfer them.	US1
SUC 4	Connect source repositories to F2DS	Inserm prototype repo, F2DS prototype	Done	#6.6	As a researcher, I would like to access a subset of genomics data from a given cohort in order to perform analysis/computation on these data without having to transfer them.	US1
SUC 5	Allow access to reference data (available in data repositories) from different Galaxy deployments	Laniakea@ReC AS authN and authZ mechanisms, IFB Galaxy	Done	#6.6	As a data provider (health data) I would like to be sure the data I'm taking care of are both properly secured and yet accessible to various computational tools so that they can be useful to researchers	US3
SUC 6	Facilitate the deployment of Galaxy instances close to the data	Laniakea@ReC AS, IFB Galaxy, Public DBs	Done	#6.6	As a developer, I would like to be able to deploy Galaxy on different Cloud infrastructures across Europe transparently in order to implement and make available new tools and workflows very quickly on the different data spaces available to me.	US4
SUC 7	Provide coherency between different existing Galaxy deployments	Laniakea@ReC AS, IFB Galaxy	Done	#6.6	As a developer, I would like to be able to deploy Galaxy on different Cloud infrastructures across Europe transparently in order to implement and make available new tools and workflows very quickly on the different data spaces available to me.	US4
SUC 8	Ensure health data privacy are met throughout the data management process	INFN Cloud	Done	#6.6	As a healthcare provider interested in personalized medicine, I would like to be able to use GDPR compliant Galaxy instances deployed over Cloud infrastructures across Europe so I could safely process patient's data.	US5

Tab. 1 Requirements for demonstrator #6.6

Demonstrator #6.2 - Agile FAIR Data for Environment and Earth System Communities

Objective: Earth environment sciences and geosciences require a large panel and volume of data from satellite, in-situ observations and climate models, that are managed and preserved separately in domain-dependant repositories of national or European infrastructures. As the data sources are

widely distributed, it induces real difficulties to achieve inter-processing and integrated uses of the data for comprehensive studies at domain or cross-domain level.

In this context, the goal is to offer services that facilitate and speed up the access to the distributed data sources and provide a web-based processing environment for Data Science notebooks supporting the Pangeo community platform.

Targeted users: The web-based processing environment proposed by the use case have to address the needs of two types of users of Data Science notebooks on Earth environment & Geosciences data: scientists and data analysts.

Sub use-case#	Title	Dependency on other resource/services	Status	Demonstrator#	User stories	User story#
SUC9	Have access to big datasets from distributed data sources	FG-iRODS: Use an iRODS instance(s) as a distributed data repository for sharing big datasets	Done	#6.2	As a modeler I would like to make use of data from different earth observation compartments such as ocean/atmosphere or sea/land in order to study and to model the processes at the interface, that means: b. I would expect that data would be accessible through an uniform API	US6
SUC10	Find and compare satellite data and in-situ observation	Jupyter notebook (D4Science @CNR)	Done	#6.2	As a data processing developer, I would like to colocalize satellite data and in-situ observations in order to compare the “ground truth” and remote sensing in order to calibrate my processing tools and to detect biases and outliers in processing outputs, that means: a. I would like to easily find and identify what are the available in-situ datasets of the pertinent variables which match in space and time with my areas of interest	US7
SUC11	Access/use SW configured in conda environments setup to create/deploy python application programs	VRE equipped with conda package	Done	#6.2	As a data processing developer, I would like to colocalize satellite data and in-situ observations in order to compare the “ground truth” and remote sensing in order to calibrate my processing tools and to detect biases and outliers in processing outputs, that means: b. I would expect to compute and to display at a large extend	US8

					the differences between the two data sources.	
SUC12	Perform analysis using notebook on demand on data of interest from remote facilities	Jupyter notebook (D4Science @CNR), CINES; FG-iRODS (data source)	Done	#6.2	As a data processing developer, I would like to colocalize satellite data and in-situ observations in order to compare the “ground truth” and remote sensing in order to calibrate my processing tools and to detect biases and outliers in processing outputs, that means: b. I would expect to compute and to display at a large extend the differences between the two data sources.	US9
SUC13	Format datasets based on standard climate model CMIP5, CMIP6	CMIP6 climate model data (~3 PByte), local intake catalog, CMCC models contribution to CMIP5	Done	#6.2	As a modeler I would like to make use of data from different earth observation compartments such as ocean/atmosphere or sea/land in order to study and to model the processes at the interface, that means: such as ocean/atmosphere or sea/land in order to study and to model the processes at the interface, that means: a. I would expect that data are organized in the same way (“same format”),	US10
SUC14	Run ready-to-use data processing scripts on temporal and geographical areas of interest	Ifremer(HPC-DATARMOR), DKRZ (HPC), CMCC(ECAS cluster)	Done	#6.2	As a data processing developer, I would like to colocalize satellite data and in-situ observations in order to compare the “ground truth” and remote sensing in order to calibrate my processing tools and to detect biases and outliers in processing outputs	US7, US8

Tab. 2 Requirements for demonstrator #6.2

Demonstrator #6.3 - Integration of Data repositories into EOSC based on communities' approaches

Objective: The Use Case 6.3 demonstrator is to explore the current limitations and provide concrete recommendations and tools to address preservation, re-usability and reproducibility of data repositories. This will be achieved using existing Agrifood and Health sciences Dataverse and iRODS implementations, two data and metadata repository implementations used for storage, management and publication. However, the developed tools and connectors will be discipline or community agnostic and will enrich the whole EOSC services ecosystem.

Targeted users: The demonstrator aims to address the needs of the AgriFood community based on scientific user stories, notably the phenotyping community represented by PHENOME-EMPHASIS researchers. However, as the task deliverables are generic interoperability connectors, the potential users also include all Dataverse based repository users, and EOSC marketplace users for the Data In the cloud deliverables.

Sub use-case#	Title	Dependency on other resource/services	Status	Demonstrator #	User stories	User story #
SUC15	Access GPU Resources through containers through jupyterhub	GPU Container - Kubernetes	Done	#6.3	As a modeler I would like to be able to run my models online/on-demand infrastructure service without worrying about the technical aspects	US11
SUC16	Perform analysis (using notebook) on demand on data of interest from a data repository	Data INRAE: data repository Kubernetes Cluster JupyterHub	In progress	#6.3	As a scientist, from a Dataverse based data repository, I would like to be able to export a dataset contents in an external tool in in order to reproduce the results and produce new results. a. As external tool, I would like to use: Jupyterhub; Renku; Binder	US12
SUC17	Publish computing scripts and results	Data INRAE: data repository	Done	#6.3	As a researcher, I would like to be able to publish my online edited scripts and the outputted data directly in order to avoid multiple uploads/downloads and facilitate the dataset publication.	US13
SUC18	Share and access big datasets stored in an iRODS zone to perform further analysis	FG-iRODS	Done	#6.3	As a researcher, I would like to be able to access and share datasets very big in size among the community to perform analysis.	US14
SUC19	Archive data and metadata from data repositories	Data INRAE: data repository, Vitam: archive, CINES iRODS	In progress	#6.3	As a data producer I would like to have my data preserved on the long run in order to be compliant with legal and scientific needs of long-term	US15

					access to my data.	
SUC20	Make a link between INRAE data repository and D4Science	Data INRAE: data repository, D4Science: EOSCPillar4Agri Food VRE	In progress	#6.3	As a researcher, I would like to be able to export my datasets content from a Dataverse based data repository of D4Science Virtual Research Environment. In order to be able to exploit all the computing operations offered by the VRE.	US16
SUC21	Access external jupyterhub instances from D4Science VRE	D4Science: EOSCPillar4Agri Food VRE	In progress	#6.3	As a researcher, I would like to be able to choose the platform used for my analyses from the VRE in order to use a platform providing the complementary tools I need	US17
SUC22	Make use of existing tools from Material Marketplace on the data from INRAE repository	IWM Material Marketplace, Laniakea service	In progress	#6.3	As a researcher, I would like to be able to access the datasets deposited in my data repository (Dataverse based) in MarketPlace in order to use the tools provided by the marketplace on my datasets.	US18
SUC23	Connect Dataverse based data repository to F2DS	Data INRAE: data repository F2DS: Federated data space D4Science: federated data catalog	Done	#6.3	As a data producer I would like to have my data exposed on a catalogue (F2DS) in order to improve its visibility. a. From Dataverse to be able to use data retrieval APIs b. From D4Science VRE as provided by this service	US19

Tab. 3 Requirements for demonstrator #6.3

Demonstrator #6.5 Share and analyse LIDAR data as a service

Objective: An additional sub-use-case of T6.5 (from Amendment v.2: 2021-11), also targeting the SSH community, will be developed starting from M28, aiming to promote open data and collaborative work on huge LIDAR (Light Detection and Ranging) datasets. The ultimate goal of the activity is to provide a tool to analyse human impact on the Earth's surface. Within EOSC-Pillar, the sub-use case will, in collaboration with the Archeoscape project and also leveraging T7.4 expertise and resources, build a PoC to tackle the challenges of storing, sharing, aggregating, searching and retrieving large distributed datasets (tens of TBs).
Targeted users: Researchers using LIDAR datasets: Collaborating on data sharing, methodology, FAIRness of LIDAR data;

Archaeologists working on Southeast Asia and beyond: Using the GIS web platform to visualise data regarding specific areas, download full LIDAR raw dataset, upload data in order to analyse them through deep learning.

Sub use-case#	Description	Dependency on other resource/services	Status	Demonstrator #	User stories	User story #
SUC24	Run a scalable version of the Archeoscape service	Container as a Service (CNRS), Storage (Hum-Num)	In progress	#6.5	In order to promote open data and collaborative work on huge LIDAR datasets, the project aims to develop a scalable framework for aggregating, sharing and collaborating on LIDAR datasets. One of the challenges is to deploy the RVT toolbox ⁴ on the Cloud infrastructure.	US20
SUC25	Access GPU resources for AI workflow	GPUaaS (CNRS)	In progress	#6.5	In order to move beyond localised, culturally-specific LIDAR applications, one of our goal is to build on recent advances in artificial intelligence to develop generic models for automation and analysis.	US21

Tab. 4 Requirements for demonstrator #6.5

2.2.2 List of the derived technical requirements

We derive the technical requirements reported by the technical and development team of each service/resource provider. There were 23 technical requirements collected. We show only an excerpt list of them in Tab. 5.

Technical Requirement ID	Description	EOSC Pillar resource/service utilization	Sub use cases#	Gap	Status	Priority
RQ1	Configure custom Galaxy settings during installation, install	Laniakea@ReCAS	SUC5	No	Done	Normal

⁴ <https://www.zrc-sazu.si/en/rvt>

	cvmfs_client					
RQ2	Integrate a dedicated openstack tenant close to the data available at Laniakea@ReCAS resources	Laniakea@ReCAS	SUC6	No	Done	High
RQ3	Use of Official Galaxy community Ansible Roles	Laniakea@ReCAS	SUC7	No	Done	Normal
RQ4	Implement/test connection to the API as inputs for Galaxy	Laniakea@ReCAS	SUC5, SUC6	No	Done	Normal
RQ5	Deploy a Galaxy instance using cloud resources under the GDPR compliancy	INFN computing INFRA	SUC8	No	Done	Normal
RQ6	Resource providers integration with INDIGO-IAM	Laniakea@ReCAS	SUC5, SUC7, SUC8	No	Done	Normal
RQ7	Describe API requests to retrieve datasets	F2DS	SUC3, SUC4	No	In progress	Normal
RQ8	Provide the mapping to map dataset metadata to DCAT properties	F2DS	SUC3, SUC4	No	In progress	Normal
RQ9	Deploy a VM with a Dataverse sw installed and configured	Dataverse VM	SUC1, SUC2	No	Done	High
[..]	[..]	[..]	[..]	[..]	[..]	[..]

Tab. 5 An excerpt list of derived Technical Requirements

And in Tab. 6 we show a summary of the progress achieved by thematic services and one generic service (GPUaaS) during the project, if a change management system is designed and if a CI/CD agile model is being used from the provider's side. More detail information about this we give in the Appendix-2.

EOSC Pillar resource/service	Nr of Sub-use cases	Nr of User Stories	Total technical requirements	Change management system (CMS)			Description
				Gaps	Yes/No	CI system used (link)	
Laniakea@ReCAS	6	5	5	No	Yes	https://github.com/Laniakea-elixir-it	GitHub instance/Jenkins tool
GPUaaS	3	3	3	No	No	N/A	No CI/CD model used

						https://support.d4science.org	Redmine-based ticketing system for user support
VRE/VLab	7	7	7	No	Yes	https://wiki.gcube-system.org/gcube/Continuous_Integration_procedure_(2019)	CI procedure documentation
FG-iRODS	2	2	2	No	Yes	https://gitlab.in2p3.fr/	GitLab service instance using Puppet module
Pico2	1	1	2	No	No	N/A only a source code configuration system: https://gitlab.inria.fr https://gitlab.cc-asp.fraunhofer.de/	GitLab instance for source code (build/test) configuration
Oyster	-	-	-	No	Yes	https://github.com/materials-marketplace/	GitLab private instance for source code
ReadMetrics	-	-	-	No	Yes	https://github.com/ezparse-project/readmetrics/	GitHub instance
MMODA	-	-	-	No	Yes	https://github.com/oda-hub/doc-handbook	GitHub instance

Tab. 6 Summary of progress achieved by the services in EOSC-Pillar

3. EOSC-Pillar Available Resources/Services

3.1 Summary of the services

The services described below were identified after three successive steps: scientific use cases (WP6, e.g., T6.6 scenario 3 implementation), open call for communities (WP6.10, e.g., MModa) and survey (WP7, e.g., Laniakea E-initiative) as depicted in the timeline of Fig. 2

Fig. 2 Timeline of collection of services within Pillar project

The service providers then performed a self-assessment based on a questionnaire to provide further details on technology implementation and service levels. The information gathered this way was used to itemize the products in the following sub-sections. In addition, to assess the maturity level of each service from the service delivery perspective a tool was adopted from a collaboration activity with the EOSC Nordic project ⁵. Subsequent analysis indicates the compliance degree on the service delivery requirement for each service selected as a case study. More details are reported in the D7.3 Report on the Validation statistics, operational infrastructure services and recommendations for future integration work (Berberi, van Wezel and Breton 2021) on service validation statistics.

The thematic services are summarized based on their availability, implemented use case, deployment status, TRL and AAI interface in the Tab. 7 below.

Two services received from the open call are not listed in the following table as they joined the project last October with the aim to support them to be part of the EOSC ecosystem.

⁵ <https://www.eosc-nordic.eu/>

Service	GPU container (Subtask 7.4.1)	Laniakea (Subtask 7.4.2)	Virtual Laboratories/ Virtual Research Environment s supporting collaboration (Subtask 7.4.3)	Virtual Research Environment-based service for research data publishing (Subtask 7.4.4)	Pico2	Oyster/Marketplace
AAI proxy	EGI-checkin	Indigo-IAM	EOSC Portal AAI	EOSC Portal AAI	Indigo-IAM (in progress)	Indigo-IAM
Use case implementation	UC6.2	UC6.6	UC6.3, UC 6.5	overall data catalogue: https://eosc-pillar.d4science.org/group/eosc-pillarresdatactlg WP5.3 guidelines and training resource data stewardship	UC6.3	UC6.3
Deployment status	ready	ready	ready	ready	ready	ready
TRL	8	9	9	9	8	8
Endpoint	OpenStack Horizon dashboard	https://laniakea-dashboard.cloud.ba.infn.it	EOSC-Pillar gateway	EOSC-Pillar resource training catalogue	https://gitlab.inria.fr/biodiversityseq	https://www.materials-marketplace.eu

Tab. 7 First list of EOSC-Pillar thematic services and their integration with specific use-cases

Some project partners also offered to provide “in-kind” service contribution for the duration of the project, which could be available for the use of other participants. These are recapped in Tab. 8.

Service	iRODS (CNRS)	iRODS (CINES)	iRODS (KIT)	iRODS (CINECA)	Cloud and HPC-Generic services (CINECA)
AAI service	Indigo-IAM Pillar AAI instance (working progress)	B2Safe module installed and interfaced with B2ACCESS	B2Safe module installed (B2ACCESS interface-working)	B2Safe module installed and interfaced with B2ACCESS	Currently it is possible to have an access to our HPC machines mainly using ssh.
Use case implementation	UC6.2	Not yet	UC6.7	Not yet	Not yet
Deployment status	ready	ready	ready	ready	ready
TRL	8	8	9	9	9

Tab. 8 List of in-kind EOSC-Pillar services and their integration with specific use-cases

3.2 Laniakea-Galaxy

Short description:

Laniakea is a software framework that facilitates the provisioning of on-demand Galaxy instances as a cloud service over e-infrastructures. The Laniakea based service, Laniakea@ReCaS, provided by ELIXIR-IT is a European Open Science Cloud provider. The service is available in the EOSC Marketplace⁶

Architecture outlined and technical specifications:

Laniakea leverages the open source PaaS layer developed by the INDIGO-DataCloud project. The user interacts with Laniakea through its dashboard, a web front-end that allows, in a very straightforward way, the configuration and subsequently the deployment of a production-grade Galaxy instance. The PaaS layer provides the orchestration services and exploiting the Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure, based on INDIGO IAM, automates the deployment, configuration, software installation, and monitoring of the virtual Galaxy servers.

⁶ <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/laniakea-recas>

In addition, Laniakea also exploits other open-source software to provide advanced configurations, to provide ready-to-use Galaxy servers. In particular

- LUKS to encrypt persistent storage associated with each Galaxy instance.
- CERN-VM File System⁷ repository for Reference data provisioning.

The architecture of Laniakea is shown in the following figure (Fig. 3):

Fig. 3 Architecture of Laniakea

Laniakea provides the documentation for end users, administrators and developers. In particular, a detailed step-by-step guide on how to correctly deploy the service and the recommended resources needed is provided at this page⁸.

Outcomes - successful deployments and operations

Laniakea@ReCaS, is an ELIXIR-Italy Galaxy on-demand cloud service, based on Laniakea, and hosted at the ReCaS-Bari datacenter. The ReCaS cloud platform that hosts the service is based on OpenStack, with about 1700 CPU cores, 6.7 TB of RAM and 270 TB of storage (replica 3).

Laniakea is mainly implemented on the **usecase 6.6** of WP6 in the EOSC-Pillar project, whose main objectives are (1) to ensure the reproducibility and coherency of the data analysis (performed on different platforms) and (2) conform to data protection regulations concerning health personal data.

⁷ <https://cernvm.cern.ch/fs/>

⁸ <https://laniakea.readthedocs.io>

The Laniakea core, which is responsible for the Galaxy configuration, has been completely revised, to exploit the official GalaxyProject ansible roles allowing for faster alignment of Laniakea flavours to the latest Galaxy releases. Moreover, a continuous Integration framework, based on Jenkins has been deployed for automatic flavour testing, update, and implementation. The reproducibility of the analysis between a private deployment of Galaxy through Laniakea and a public instance manually configured, has been tested developing a specific "Somatic Variant Detection" Galaxy flavour. The test was recorded and presented as a demo at a F2F meeting dedicated to WP6, the video was then published on the YouTube channel ⁹ dedicated to the project, showing that using the same workflow and the same input data, we obtained identical output.

Finally, concerning data protection for health personal data, the procedure to deploy encrypted storage has been extended to be usable with any application deployable with Laniakea (and the INDIGO PaaS), as for example JupyterHub and RStudio. Moreover, it is now possible to deploy Galaxy instances on private net, accessible through a VPN, using users IAM credentials.

3.2.1 Galaxy-E for Ecology Initiative

Short description:

Galaxy-E¹⁰ is a web platform to get, process, analyse and visualise *ecological* data. It is listed as a platform of the Galaxy project¹¹, which consists of wide range of resources covering a wide spectrum of domains all across life sciences. A Galaxy-E Community¹² is devoted to the creation of resources for ecology research conducted through the Galaxy project.

Architecture outlined and technical specifications:

⁹ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SK9C_MWz6Yk&t=68s

¹⁰ <https://galaxyproject.org/use/ecology/>

¹¹ <https://galaxyproject.org/>

¹² <https://github.com/galaxyecology/tools-ecology>

Fig. 4 Galaxy-E initiative Overview

In Fig. 4 we give an overview of the Galaxy-E initiative where the platform components are illustrated (e.g., infrastructure, workflows, tools, packaging etc.). This platform is developed and maintained thanks to the financial support given by different projects (respective project icons are positioned in the bottom line).

A user may use the service free of charge with limited computational resources by providing his/her institutional credentials through the Life Science Login¹³ as a common gateway to the European Life Sciences research Infrastructures or can register using the registration form.

Outcomes - successful deployments and operations

A direct contribution from the EOSC-Pillar project is the development of the tutorial¹⁴, specifically the tutorial on how to compute biodiversity metrics¹⁵. Another task was to update the PAMPA tool suite¹⁶ and testing for the following use cases:

- French Breeding Bird survey data ¹⁷ in STOC galaxy-E history repo
- Submarine camera data(fish) in Marine Protected Area Galaxy-E history¹⁸
- DATRAS ICES data (fish capture) in DATRAS ICES Galaxy-E history ¹⁹
- Acoustic data citizen science (bats) in Vigie-Chiro Galaxy-E history ²⁰

¹³ <https://profile.aai.lifescience-ri.eu/>

¹⁴ <https://training.galaxyproject.org/>

¹⁵ <https://training.galaxyproject.org/training-material/topics/ecology/tutorials/PAMPA-toolsuite-tutorial/tutorial.html>

¹⁶ <https://github.com/galaxyecology/tools-ecology/tree/master/tools/PAMPA>

¹⁷ https://ecology.usegalaxy.eu/u/coline_royaux/h/stoc-data-on-pampa-workflow

¹⁸ https://ecology.usegalaxy.eu/u/coline_royaux/h/donnes-staviro-amp-nouma---pampa-workflow

¹⁹ https://ecology.usegalaxy.eu/u/coline_royaux/h/datras-full---pampa-workflow

²⁰ https://ecology.usegalaxy.eu/u/coline_royaux/h/donnes-vigie-chiro

- Reef life Survey citizen science project in Reef life survey Galaxy-E history²¹

3.3 GPU container as a Service

Short description:

Since 2013, France Grilles operates a distributed Cloud infrastructure hosted and administered by ten resource providers. They allow users to globally access a set of 10,000 cores and 2500 TB of storage.

In order to facilitate the use of this infrastructure by users, the offer includes several services:

- Training and documentation
- Unified access
- Privileged access to the France Grilles iRODS infrastructure
- Bridge with the EGI Federated Cloud

A container-based service has been recently added to meet user's needs and to face new challenges of scientific research. It permits to instantiate Kubernetes clusters, with the possibility to use GPUs. This service is currently available only on a single site hosted by the SCIGNE platform.

Architecture outlined and technical specifications:

The SCIGNE Cloud infrastructure is composed of 1320 cores and 500 TB of storage. It offers also access to GPU resources.

Kubernetes clusters can be created using the OpenStack Magnum module available on the Horizon dashboard or by using Terraform ²² recipes.

The following type of GPUs are currently available:

- NVIDIA Tesla P100
- NVIDIA Tesla T4

Outcomes - successful deployments and operations

The service is successfully used by three use cases: WP6.2, WP6.3 and WP6.5. A complete documentation has been written and the website has been translated in English language²³.

A container hub²⁴ has been put on-line to facilitate the usage of container across computing infrastructures. It permits to store the GPU containers that can be used by this service.

The GPU as a service has been on-boarded on the EOSC Marketplaces²⁵.

²¹ https://ecology.usegalaxy.eu/u/coline_royaux/h/reeflifedata-on-pampa

²² <https://www.terraform.io/>

²³ <https://grand-est.fr/en/services/on-demand-servers-and-containers>

²⁴ <https://csanhub.org/>

²⁵ <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/scigne-cloud-computes>

3.4 VRE/VLab using D4Science technology

Short description:

D4Science (M. Assante, et al. 2019a) is an infrastructure offering a rich array of services operated by exploiting the gCube open source software system (M. Assante, et al. 2019b). Among the distinguishing features of this infrastructure and its offering there are the following:

- it enacts the deployment and operation of virtual research environments, i.e., web based working environments that are community-driven and co-created;
- it offers a rich array of services for supporting collaborative open science practices including a customisable catalogue for publishing and searching community defined items;
- it enacts hybrid and participatory operation scenarios where the services offered by every VRE can be operated on D4Science premises as well as on service providers that may be integrated with D4Science in several ways.

Architecture outlined and technical specifications:

Every VRE/VLab realises a web-based working environment for a community to collaborate. It offers some basic and community agnostic services (e.g., workspace, social networking, user management) that can be complemented by community specific services to be integrated. The service is ready to use. VLab/VREs are operated by D4Science.org²⁶ while the services integrated in them can be operated by other providers. VREs/VLabs when created will be available by the EOSC-Pillar gateway²⁷.

Regarding **AuthN** D4Science currently interfaces with the EOSC Portal federation/proxy as well as Google and LinkedIn.

Regarding **AuthZ** D4Science uses a role-based mechanism where roles are defined and assigned in D4Science/VREs.

The service includes computing resources. Additional storage resources can be made available through the iRODS service.

Among the basic services every VRE has a workspace, which resembles a file system in the cloud. Upon request it is possible to deploy an analytics platform for running algorithms on a distributed computing infrastructure.

For the development of a catalogue concept the D4Science offering can be mobilised as depicted in the diagram below of Fig. 5.

²⁶ <http://www.d4science.org/>

²⁷ <https://eosc-pillar.d4science.org/>

Fig. 5 The D4Science-driven Approach: Overall Architecture

The Figure above depicts how the services of every virtual research environment are connected and can be exploited to support the development of the data space of interest for the designated community:

- the primary service is a catalogue, i.e., a service the community can use to have a unifying access point to content either collected from existing data sources or explicitly published into the catalogue instance.
- every VRE provides its users with a workspace for storing and organising material of interest. It realises a cloud-based shared file system the community can use to store files representing the payload of items to be published into the catalogue as well as contents to be exploited by other services the VRE offers.
- every VRE provides its users with a social networking for communicating among members of the working environment.

Every VRE provides its users with user management functionalities (e.g., invite new members, manage memberships, manage roles) and usage indicators (e.g., log ins, items published, interactions taking place).

Outcomes - successful deployments and operations

Different instantiations of the D4Science based catalogue solution are available:

- regarding **catalogue content population**, two complementary approaches are supported: harvesting, and publishing.
- regarding **catalogue content consumption**, the catalogue offers its content via a specific GUI enacting to search and browse as well as accessing the items (and any of the resources accompanying them) as well as by approaches and standards including RESTful Web API (gCat²⁸), DCAT²⁹, and OAI-PMH³⁰.)

²⁸ https://wiki.gcube-system.org/gcube/GCat_Service

One instance of the overall data catalogue has been created and made available by the EOSC-Pillar Data Catalogue Virtual Research Environment³¹.

Some instance of community driven virtual research environments, stemming from the use cases in WP6 have been deployed and we list them as follows:

- EOSC-Pillar 4 AgriFood³²
- EOSC-Pillar 4 Earth Science³³
- EOSC-Pillar 4 COVID-19³⁴
- The service registry³⁵
- The research data catalogue³⁶

Another example of a community driven catalogue³⁷ is the one set up for supporting the activity of the Tasks 5.3 and 5.4 dealing with training and support material.

3.5 FG-iRODS

Short description:

FG-iRODS is a data management service designed to meet the needs of researchers. Access to the resources is open to all scientific communities and is interoperable with other commonly deployed data storage systems. This service is positioned as complementary to other players in the field and is intended for small and medium-sized projects. Its main objectives are:

- to provide a production level (TRL8) service for scientific data management;
- to make distributed data storage technologies accessible;
- to offer dedicated support to users.

The iRODS engine offers the following features:

- virtualisation of storage access;
- management of several petabytes of data;
- parallelization of large data transfers;
- metadata management;
- process automation;

²⁹ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-2/>

³⁰ <https://www.openarchives.org/pmh/>

³¹ <https://eosc-pillar.d4science.org/group/eoscpillarresdatactlg>

³² <https://eosc-pillar.d4science.org/group/eosc-pillar-gateway/explore?siteId=275679981>

³³ <https://eosc-pillar.d4science.org/group/eosc-pillar-gateway/explore?siteId=290355595>

³⁴ <https://eosc-pillar.d4science.org/group/eosc-pillar-gateway/explore?siteId=275455785>

³⁵ <https://eosc-pillar.d4science.org/group/bluecloud-gateway/explore?siteId=197265081>

³⁶ <https://eosc-pillar.d4science.org/group/bluecloud-gateway/explore?siteId=223570673>

³⁷ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/training-and-support-catalogue>

- data security through replication and fine-grained access management.

Architecture outlined and technical specifications:

The infrastructure currently comprises seven sites across France and provides users the access to 1.3 petabytes of storage. The entire infrastructure was renewed in 2018. It runs the iRODS software and is accessible through the iRODS client, SDK and the MetalNX Web portal³⁸.

Outcomes - successful deployments and operations

The access has been open to users from WP6.2, WP6.3 and WP6.5.

The documentation has been translated in English language to be usable by most European researchers.

The work on-going is the integration to the EOSC Pillar AAI.

3.6 Pico2

Short description:

Follow-up of EOSC-Pilot, PICO2

Within EOSC-Pilot, PICO2 (Pilot for Connecting Computing Centres) was an initiative aiming at facilitating data and code flows between HPC and HTC infrastructures at regional, national and European level, being agnostic as far as scientific communities were concerned. The centres involved were national (IDRIS, CC-IN2P3, France Grilles, DESY Germany) or regional ones (GRICAD Grenoble, MCIA and PlaFRIM Bordeaux³⁹, GRIF CEA Orsay) and RENATER.

Several areas of work were addressed during the EOSCPilot project:

- Data sharing through an IRODS zone federation;
- Dedicated network connection via L3VPN;
- Evaluation of different code carrying solutions: packaging and container systems.

In EOSC-Pillar, Pico2 is focused on deploying tools on HPC infrastructures while easing their use for non-HPC specialists (biologists of the metabarcoding community) through access to computing facilities via Galaxy servers and/or Jupyter hubs.

Architecture outlined and technical specifications:

³⁸ <https://metalnx.fedcloud.fr>

³⁹ <https://www.plafrim.fr/>

Tools have been installed and tested on a dedicated VM provided by GRICAD, This VM contains a Galaxy server, and is expected to be a gateway to the computing nodes of DAHU the HPCDA platform at GRICAD⁴⁰.

Such an access has been successfully tested, both on PlaFRIM as the development platform with Slurm, and on GRICAD as the production service with OAR.

Deployment of the Galaxy server. Opening to the public in progress.

Interface with WP6.3 Dataverse instance operational for connecting data and computing (download tested, upload in progress)

Outcomes - successful deployments and operations

The following steps have been successfully deployed:

- public access of the tools on a public git ⁴¹
- deployment of the tools on two regional centres: PlaFRIM at Bordeaux and GRICAD at Grenoble
- deployment of a Galaxy server on each of these centres, as a node or a virtual machine
- distribution of the MPI version of the code on the computing nodes of GRICAD, either as a cli from the VM, or through a Galaxy server
- connection between data (in INRAE Dataverse) and codes deployment (either from Git or from Software Heritage) publicly accessible.

Current efforts are on letting all this publicly available while complying with the security specifications of the computing centres hosting the executable.

3.7 OYSTER and MarketPlace

Short description

This task serves the materials research community and will integrate the Materials and Models Marketplace (MarketPlace) and the Open Innovation Environment (OIE) from the OYSTER project in the EOSC framework. As a result, the services can run independently for a wide range of communities and in particular support Virtual Research Environments (VRE). Because of timing and minimal requirement issues between the contributing projects and EOSC-Pillar, the project amendment of November 2021 removed the FORCE-BDSS/VIMMP platforms from the task and exchanged them with OIE, in addition to the MarketPlace.

The European Materials Modelling Council (EMMC) coordinates and supports actions towards mechanisms that enable rapid transfer of materials modelling from academic innovation to the end

⁴⁰ <https://gricad.univ-grenoble-alpes.fr/>

⁴¹ <https://gitlab.inria.fr/biodiversiton/disseq>

users and beneficiaries in industry. The EMMC promotes a set of European Materials & Modelling technologies developed in a number of (EU) projects to support its mission. For two technologies, OIE and MarketPlace, EOSC-Pillar has provided support with EOSC integration.

OIE is a web-based platform that semantically connects characterisation experts and data by using the European EMMO ontology and the CHADA model and was developed in the OYSTER project (2017-2022).

The MarketPlace is developed by a consortium of European educational institutes and companies. MarketPlace will deliver a digital European hub to ease the access of industry to materials modelling and data repositories. The concept of the MarketPlace is to leverage recent software engineering and ICT advances to collect, adapt and integrate all scattered modelling components from all fragmented materials modelling and industrial communities and provide a single point of access to all materials modelling activities in Europe. MarketPlace develops ontologies for a number of subjects in the modelling communities in order to enable integration.

While the MarketPlace focusses on the materials modelling community, the OYSTER project targets the materials characterisation community. OYSTER'S Open Innovation Environment (OIE) is a web-based platform that semantically connects experts and data by using the EMMO ontology and the CHADA model. The combination of the MarketPlace and OYSTER projects offers the possibility of onboarding services for two domains of materials science, reaching a wide variety of experts.

With the assistance of EOSC-Pillar, MarketPlace and OIE are integrated in the EOSC framework and users of the platforms can log into the platform using their EOSC credentials by utilizing the OAuth 2.0 mechanism. However, the platforms are not yet public pending the resolution of legal issues related to GDPR.

Architecture outlined and technical specifications:

Both platforms follow a modular design where the different individual components (i.e., services) are packaged in standalone Docker images. This allows for an easier update and deployment that does not require the redeployment of modules that have not been modified.

User management is handled via Keycloak, where multiple identity providers have been added (GitHub, GitLab, EMMC, EOSC-Pillar's Indigo AIM).

The MarketPlace source code is currently hosted in Fraunhofer's private GitLab instance⁴². All requirements and definitions of the CI/CD are managed there.

In a document repository, general issues from the consortium members are gathered, and these are further refined and assigned to the specific module/repository by the developers, where they will be addressed.

Apart from individual deployments in use by developers, there is a staging instance to test the changes before deploying to production. The deployments are handled by GitLab CI/CD and staging

⁴² <https://gitlab.cc-asp.fraunhofer.de/>

happens automatically when changes are pushed to the main branch. Production deployments require a manual trigger. Some public content is already available on GitHub, in preparation to the official opening of the platform.

Outcomes - successful deployments and operations

The MarketPlace platform has a production deployment⁴³ and a staging⁴⁴ (use for testing before moving to production). A forum for discussions is available via the address⁴⁵. Additional public resources are available via the GitHub page of the platform⁴⁶. These are namely the getting-started template project for application registration and the user docs⁴⁷ whose deployment is available.

The OYSTER OIE is available in <https://oyster-oie.eu> and its docs are hosted within the platform in this link: <https://oyster-oie.eu/docs>.

3.8 ReadMetrics

Short description:

ReadMetrics is an Open and comprehensive toolkit for a common handling of usage data of electronic resources provided by Publishers or generated by institutions. It is based on the already existing and field-tested ezPAARSE and ezMESURE Free and open source tools, extending and including features inspired by the National Library of Luxembourg's transition to Open Access. A virtual analytics environment specialized into usage statistics is supplied through ReadMETRICS thanks to an Elastic and Kibana stack. Through the EOSC-Pillar project this service aims at reaching out to potential new users, potentially deploying many on-demand ezPAARSE or ReadMetrics instances in a virtualised environment and testing the integration of the Indigo-IAM Authentication and Authorization framework.

Architecture outlined and technical specifications:

The service is currently at TRL 7 and it is based on two TRL 9 services, ezPAARSE⁴⁸ and ezMESURE⁴⁹.

The service storage capacity, based on a consortium of 65+institutions, is described in the following picture:

⁴³ <https://www.materials-marketplace.eu>

⁴⁴ <https://staging.materials-marketplace.eu>

⁴⁵ <https://forum.materials-marketplace.eu>

⁴⁶ <https://github.com/materials-marketplaces>

⁴⁷ <https://materials-marketplace.readthedocs.io/en/latest>

⁴⁸ <https://www.ezpaarse.org/>

⁴⁹ <https://ezmeasure.couperin.org/>

Fig. 6 Architecture of ezMESHURE

The ezMESHURE stack already relies on the identity federation (through Renater) and should be able to use EduGAIN at European level. SAML⁵⁰ standard is adopted for the service’s Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure.

Outcomes - successful deployments and operations

At the moment of writing there is an on-going work both for deploying a public ReadMetrics portal that will contain demo usage data served from Inist-CNRS local infrastructure and implement the possibility of individual accounts creation. In order to handle those account creations and management, there is the willingness to integrate the ReadMetrics instance with a local IAM-Indigo containerised instance .

3.9 MMODA

Short description:

MMODA (Multi-Messenger Online Data Analysis, formerly known as AstroODA - Astrophysical Online Data Analysis) is a web-based service for the analysis of astrophysical data. The service allows users to leverage cloud-based scientific data analysis workflows of astrophysical observatories and experiments, providing verified publication-ready results.

⁵⁰ <http://saml.xml.org/>

The MMODA thematic service in the EOSC marketplace provides access to unique astrophysical data, powered by the domain expert community, as well as an extensible open source software framework for building and exchanging web-based astrophysical data analysis services, leveraged by the international community.

Architecture outlined and technical specifications:

The functional architecture of MMODA is depicted in the figure below.

Fig. 7 Architecture of MMODA

MMODA allows domain experts to develop web-based data analysis services and share them with users who consume them.

To support development, MMODA relies on cloud-native technologies, Gitlab and GitHub repositories, as well as Continuous Integration and Continuous Deployment (CI/CD) tools. This allows domain experts to contribute easily through code-to-service workflows, while allowing the tracing of result provenance to enhance result veracity and while retaining rights and credits over the code that domain experts provide.

Outcomes - successful deployments and operations

MMODA has been onboarded on the EOSC Marketplace⁵¹.

⁵¹ <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/astronomical-online-data-analysis-astrooda>

4. Support on integration with the EOSC-core services

EOSC core services⁵² are identified after EOSC-hub project as one of the most relevant EOSC implementation project. In the frame of the EOSC-Pillar project, an interest on the EOSC AAI core service was expressed by some service providers.

The most recent integration guidelines are documented in the D7.1 (Gaido, et al. 2021) based on the official ones from EOSC Portal⁵³.

A dedicated IAM instance⁵⁴ for the EOSC-Pillar project has been deployed at INFN-CNAF. The Pillar IAM instance has been registered in EduGAIN⁵⁵, and provides a registration service that implements user onboarding to the EOSC-Pillar organization.

We conducted a specific “AAI Questionnaire”⁵⁶ using Google Forms to capture key AAI requirements from research communities involved in WP6 which are utilising some common and data repositories services in order to implement their use-cases. This questionnaire was sent also to service providers of WP7.4 which are offering mostly infrastructure and thematic services. The questions have been proposed basically considering other previous surveys related to AAI topics and activities such as AARC project⁵⁷.

By conducting this questionnaire, we had a clearer idea of the needs regarding AAI solution from the community part of the EOSC-Pillar project so we can support them further in integrating/federating the proposed services.

We received five responses from coordinators of WP6 use cases that were interested to know more about this integration activity. Afterwards, individual meetings with the respective service providers’ teams have been organised to support them with technical information on integration.

Among them, there were some other services that have already interfaced their service with one EOSC-core federated AAI, for instance, with the AAI central proxy of EOSC, D4Science VRE/VLab and GPUaaS were interfaced.

There are six services that have already started the connection and integration with Indigo-IAM as listed below:

- FG-iRODS
- Laniakea-Galaxy
- Pico2 (in progress)
- Software Heritage⁵⁸ as a source-code preservation repository

⁵² <https://wiki.eosc-hub.eu/display/EOSC/Documentation+for+Federation+Services>

⁵³ <https://eosc-portal.eu/>

⁵⁴ <https://iam-pillar.cloud.cnaf.infn.it>

⁵⁵ <https://edugain.org/>

⁵⁶ <https://forms.gle/G4U8JfE2PtCD67qd7>

⁵⁷ <https://aarc-project.eu/>

⁵⁸ <https://www.softwareheritage.org/>

- Material Modelling Marketplace
- F2DS (Federated Fair Data Space⁵⁹, a meta-data repository as a prototype of the project)

The test validation suite was ready to provide evidence of integration activities with AAI since the first months of the project starting date.

Client applications and services are integrated with INDIGO IAM via standard OAuth/OpenID Connect mechanisms. The main requisite for a service that wants to be integrated with INDIGO IAM is to register itself as a client application. The client registration process sets the scopes that the application can subsequently request when authenticating a user and will translate into claims included in the access tokens issued by INDIGO IAM. Claims contain information typically used to enforce authorisation when accessing a resource, such as capabilities or membership to an organisation. At the end of the registration process, the application obtains confidential credentials that it will use when interacting with INDIGO IAM.

Fig. 8 Authentication and Authorization Flow

The diagram above is a summary of the Authentication flow. When a user tries to access a protected service, the service, following the rules defined for OIDC protocol⁶⁰, redirects user to IAM's login portal using its confidential client credentials. As soon the identity of the user is recognised with success, through local or institutional credentials, the user is redirected to the protected service. In order to explain the advantages of federated AAI for EOSC in a more general sense, a short video⁶¹

⁵⁹ <https://f2ds.eosc-pillar.eu/app/>

⁶⁰ <https://openid.net/connect/>

has been delivered. This was also intended as a contribution to the EOSC-Pillar Ambassadors Programme.

5. Support on integration with the onboarding process to EOSC catalogue/marketplace

Deliverable D7.1 (Gaido, et al. 2021) contains a lot of useful information for either service providers or user communities interested to understand how to connect with the EOSC. One of main ways to achieve this is through the onboarding of resources into the EOSC Catalogue through the EOSC Portal⁶².

During the EOSC-Pillar project, some actors have been supported to onboard their services into the EOSC Catalogue, mainly through ad-hoc calls where the main steps of the procedure have been illustrated.

Onboarding means registering an entity as Service Provider in the EOSC Portal and then, as soon as the SP application has been approved, resources (which means services for the time being) can be onboarded, too.

Although the procedure is quite straightforward, some difficulties have been encountered and this was mainly due to the unfamiliarity with the EOSC Portal terminology and background, which was the result of a number of EC-funded projects carried on over time. Currently the EOSC Portal and the associated onboarding process are supported by the EOSC Future project⁶³.

Examples of the support on integrating a service with Indigo-IAM as a core service are provided to the service providers such as: CNR-IBIOM, CNRS, INRIA, CINES, Fraunhofer that managed to successfully interface their service applications to the Indigo-IAM service endpoint.

Another important activity concerned the support for the connection of the National catalogue prototype, developed by EOSC-Pillar in task T4.4, with the EOSC Portal catalogue. For this purpose, the first step was the delivery of a document describing the steps required to operate a national or thematic catalogue which was to interoperate with the EOSC catalogue. This document, included in deliverable D7.1, has been provided to task T4.4 in order to assess its completeness and effectiveness.

The following step consisted in contributing to the definition of the procedures, processes and documentation needed to make different catalogues interoperable. Apart from the technical level of interoperability, which was under the responsibility of T4.4, the support provided by T7.1 and T7.2 concerned the policy part of this activity.

Of course, this activity, which is still ongoing, has been carried out in close collaboration with external partners/actors, specifically:

- The Regional Projects Onboarding Task Force, set up in the frame of the InfraEOSC 05 Collaboration Agreement ⁶⁴

⁶² <https://providers.eosc-portal.eu>

⁶³ <https://eoscfuture.eu/about/>

⁶⁴ <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/news-opinion/working-together-eosc-collaboration-agreement>

- The EOSC-Hub⁶⁵, EOSC- Enhance ⁶⁶ and EOSC Future ⁶⁷projects
- The EOSC Onboarding Strategy Team
- The Rules of Participation and Compliance Monitoring Task Force⁶⁸ set up by the EOSC Association⁶⁹

The main policy topic around the interoperability of catalogues concerns the agreements which should be established among the catalogue operators/owners to define the terms and conditions which have to be satisfied to allow for the interoperability. They must contain various types of information, including:

- which types of information have to be transferred from one catalogue to the other?
- what are the measures to be taken to be compliant with the GDPR when dealing with personal data?
- who retains the responsibility of ensuring that the information is up to date and it keeps being compliant with the inclusion criteria over time?
- how the validation and audit activities are performed at the different catalogues so that a trustworthy environment can be established?

In addition, it is envisaged that each catalogue owner/operator defines an agreement with its service providers to be authorised to act on their behalf when propagating their information to an external catalogue. Currently these agreements are being discussed by the EOSC Onboarding Strategy Team where all the different actors (EOSC-Future, national/regional catalogue operators and other interested parties) are represented. EOSC-Pillar representatives actively contribute to this activity.

⁶⁵ <https://www.eosc-hub.eu/>

⁶⁶ <https://eosc-portal.eu/enhance>

⁶⁷ <https://eoscfuture.eu/>

⁶⁸ <https://www.eosc.eu/advisory-groups/rules-participation-compliance-monitoring>

⁶⁹ <https://eosc.eu/>

6. Conclusions

This report discusses how the requirement gathering process and the results of the process were conducted. Also, it describes the support activities provided to the service providers to meet the criteria of being listed in the EOSC catalogue and Marketplace.

Only those services were selected and prioritised that had not been previously in the EOSC Portal or Marketplace, and which received an explicit service demand from a specific UC from: WP6: “EOSC in action: Use cases and Community driven pilots” (extracted from a template filled out during the first 6 months of the project).

IT services are rarely independent of other IT services. Apart from the connectivity with the EOSC services, in the case of EOSC-Pillar this is the AAI service and the EOSC catalogue, the services born from the scientific use cases need a place e.g., to execute, to store their data or to annotate their data. Integration of existing services with other existing services can reduce the support task for each service because they can concentrate on the development and operation of that each does best. The ‘outsourcing’ of parts of the service or using external services as building blocks for new services and workflows is a very powerful multiplier for EOSC but of course depends on interoperability on multiple levels. The work on T7.2 shows how connections with third party services can leverage existing services but also gives pointers for improvement.

The development and delivery of new services for the EOSC ecosystem is not just a technical exercise. Community efforts to deliver services need to integrate the service by connecting or federating with existing and future generic services that the EOSC core provides. From the experience learned in this project, the service providers that federated with the AAI have no difficulties in finding the proper documentation and instructions. The introductory meetings held with the AAI technical staff were welcomed and helped a smooth adoption of the software.

On the other hand, the quality requirements, most notably those dictated by the onboarding documents for the EOSC catalogue showed more difficulties. It is considered very important that right from the start, services that are part of EOSC must have a TRL of at least 7. Potential users should be provided with a reliable and sustained service if EOSC wants to live up to its promise. Therefore, the onboarding process was extensively communicated with the staff delivering the new service. The effort is part of a learning curve that the EOSC-Pillar project helped climbing. The experience is directly returned to the EOSC-Future project.

Moreover, we conducted a gap analysis to check and track which of the requirements could not be met. In case a requirement could not be met then a gap (i.e., a missing functionality/feature of a service) arises. No gaps resulted from the gap analysis we performed, only some requirements are still being resolved.

The support we gave in this report was twofold: a) integration with the AAI instance and b) integration to onboard the service into EOSC catalogue and Marketplace.

7. References

- Assante, M., L. Candela, D. Castelli, R. Cirillo, G. Coro, L. Frosini, L. Lelii, et al. 2019a. “Enacting open science by D4Science.” *Future Generation Computer Systems* 101: 555-563. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2019.05.063>.
- Assante, Massimiliano, Leonardo Candela, Donatella Castelli, Roberto Cirillo, Gianpaolo Coro, Luca Frosini, Lucio Lelii, et al. 2019b. “The gCube system: Delivering Virtual Research Environments as-a-Service.” *Future Generation Computer Systems* 95: 445-453. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2018.10.035>.
- Berberi, Lisana, Jos van Wezel, and Vincent Breton. 2021. “D7.3 Report on the validation statistics, operational infrastructure services and recommendations for future integration work.” Zenodo, #dec#. doi:10.5281/zenodo.5838072.
- Gaido, Luciano, Beatrice Chiavarini, Claudio Pisa, Fulvio Galeazzi, and Marco Verlato. 2021. “EOSC-Pillar D7.1 - Guidelines and Recommendations for the Technical Integration of Resources and Services in the EOSC.” Zenodo, #oct#. doi:10.5281/zenodo.5648215.
- Rizzo, Alessandro, Christelle Pierkot, Marine Vernet, Joël Sudre, Philipp von Hartrott, and Lisana Berberi. 2022. “EOSC-Pillar D6.2 - Demonstrators and success stories from the use cases.” Zenodo, #mar#. doi:10.5281/zenodo.6541565.

8. Appendix-1

A matrix displaying the list of the WP7 resources/services (first column) from all partners in Pillar and the demand (depicted with an 'x' in cells) expressed from UC implementations in WP6.

WP7 resources/services		WP6 usecases										New use-Case		
Resource/Service	Provider	Category	In EOSC-catalog	Status	UC#1	UC#2	UC#3	UC#4	UC#5	UC#6	UC#7	UC#8	UC#9	UC#COVID-19
Laniakea/Galaxy	INFN	Ready-to-use (7.4)	Yes	Production						X				
GPU Container	CNRS	Ready-to-use (7.4)		Production					X					
D4Science VRE	CNR (D4Science)	Ready-to-use (7.4)	Yes	Production	X	X	X			X				X
Federated FAIR Data Space (F2DS)	CINES	Ready-to-use (7.4)	Yes	Production	X	X	X			X				X
PICO2	CINES	New service		In development	X	X	X							
Marketplace	INRAE	Ready-to-use (7.4)		Production						X				
CMIP5/CMIP6 datasets	DKRZ	In kind		Production	X	X	X							
data.inrae.fr	INRAE	In kind		Production						X				
Software heritage archive	INRIA	In kind	Yes	Production		X	X							
	INFN	In kind		Production						X			X	
	KIT	In kind		Production										
	CNRS	In kind		Production					X					
Storage/computing resources	IFREMER	In kind		Production										
	CINECA	In kind		Production										
	CINES	In kind		Production										
	CNR (D4Science)	In kind		Production										X
	GARR	In kind		Production										
Cloud resources	CNRS	In kind		Production					X					
	CINECA	In kind		Production						X				
	IWM	In kind		Production										
	UNIVIE	In kind		Production										
LMS-online training platform	Trust-IT	In kind		Production										
data.ifremer.fr	IFREMER	In kind		Production										
www.odatis-ocean.fr	IFREMER	In kind		Production		X								
www.seadatanet.org	IFREMER	In kind		Production										
Datasets/metadata/ontologies	IWM	In kind		Production										
Business decision support system	IWM	In kind		Production										
Vitam	CINES	In kind		Production										
	KIT	In kind		Production										
B2Safe (IRODS)	CINECA	In kind		Production								X		
	CINES	In kind		Production										
FG-IRODS	CINES	In kind		Production										
IFB cloud Galaxy	CNRS	In kind		Production					X					
VIP	CNRS	To be onboarded		Production						X				
	CNRS	In kind	Yes	Production										X
Already a service														

9. Appendix-2

Some information about the change management system to address the new requirements and what changes are needed accordingly is shown in the list below.

<u>Change Management System (CMS)</u>	
<p><u>Laniakea-Galaxy [CMS]</u></p> <p>The main requirements coming from WP6 are faster support to new Galaxy releases, and the introduction of new applications for biological data analysis. These requirements have been addressed by upgrading the Galaxy deployment system of Laniakea, using and contributing to the ansible roles developed within the Galaxy community for faster alignment of Laniakea to the latest Galaxy instances. Moreover, new applications have been added to the Laniakea ecosystem, for example the possibility to deploy Rstudio or IRIDA instances.</p> <p>Moreover, to improve the technical long-term sustainability of Laniakea and to be able to easily manage and test the service, we decided to deploy a CI/CD (continuous integration/continuous development) service. This system is based mainly on Jenkins⁷¹, an open source automation server widely used to implement CI/CD models. Our system relies on a private Jenkins instance⁷² which can automatically create and update the new Galaxy images, and test all available Laniakea applications, in order to quickly identify bugs or temporary system failures. The documentation about the CI system is not online yet but:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Jenkins server was deployed following the tutorial⁷³, then it was modified to match Laniakea specific requirements, with additional plugins. • All the code related to the CI implementation is in our GitHub 	<p><u>GPUaaS (GPU as a Service) [CMS]</u></p> <p>Concerning the WP7.4 Container & GPU as a Service, the main requirement of WP6 was computing resources. To fulfil it, they have purchase new servers. As it was standard servers, they have used a standard procedure, and did not use the change management process.</p> <p><u>FG-iRODS [CMS]</u></p> <p>Concerning the FG-iRODS in-kind service, it was slightly different. It was not directly a need of a user, but from the project itself, to integrate the Indigo IAM AAI (but of course, user will benefit from this later). For this case, we have a specific change management process. New development is tested on a testbed and if it works perfectly, a downtime is planned (if necessary) to migrate the service in production. Documentation is updated consequently and the code required for the configuration (we are using an Infrastructure as a Code system) is stored on a git repository. Puppet is being used as the Infrastructure as a Code system. The module used are not publicly available and stored on the following GitLab service⁷⁰.</p> <p><u>VRE/VLab [CMS]</u></p> <p>Regarding D4Science, requirements (as well as support requests) coming from EOSC-pillar as well as from others are collected and managed by a (Redmine-based) ticketing system⁷⁴. The ticketing system is organised in many projects (representing diverse communities). Depending on the typology of request a dedicated team take care of its management (incident tickets are high priority, feature-requests are - if accepted - prioritised, etc.). There is a development environment (for developing new features, etc.), a pre-production environment to test the new</p>

⁷⁰ <https://gitlab.in2p3.fr/>

⁷¹ <https://www.jenkins.io/>

⁷² <https://build-usegalaxy-it.cloud.ba.infn.it>

⁷³ <https://training.galaxyproject.org/training-material/topics/admin/tutorials/jenkins/tutorial.html>

⁷⁴ <https://support.d4science.org>

<p>account⁷⁵ in particular into the repository⁷⁶.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> When ready the documentation about the CI system will be added to the Laniakea documentation⁷⁷. 	<p>versions of the services before deploying them in production, and the production infrastructure.</p> <p>The procedure governing CI/CD is fully documented⁷⁸ and there are a couple of overviews that help.</p> <p>The resulting releases are made available⁷⁹.</p> <p>The deployment of releases is planned by a dedicated team and supported by established procedures (e.g., counting on ansible scripts).</p>
<p>PICO2[CMS]</p> <p>Interface with WP6.3 Dataverse instance operational for connecting data and computing (download tested, upload in progress)</p> <p>All our code sources, documentations and configuration files are tracked with git and accessible through a Gitlab instance⁸⁰ under either public or private status (only accessible to project members).</p> <p>All the projects will be made public as soon as possible.</p> <p>There is not a CI/CD model they follow to meet the needs for agility but soon they will manage to design one.</p>	<p>OYSTER and Marketplace [CMS]</p> <p>The MarketPlace and the OYSTER OIE source code is currently hosted in Fraunhofer's private GitLab instance⁸¹. All matters related to project development and maintenance (e.g., issue tracking, milestone, automatic testing, deployment pipelines) are managed through it.</p> <p>There we maintain a designated repository for gathering general issues from the consortium members, and these are further refined and assigned to the specific module/repository by the developers, where they will be addressed.</p> <p>Apart from individual deployments that developers have, we use a staging instance for the MarketPlace, in order to test the changes before deploying to production. The deployments are handled by GitLab CI/CD, staging being automatic when changes are pushed to the main branch and production requiring to be manually triggered.</p> <p>We now have some publicly available content on GitHub⁸², in preparation to the official opening of the platform.</p> <p>There we use GitHub's CI for simple testing of the style and so on.</p>
<p>MMODA[CMS]</p> <p>All of the development is open source, most of it is on GitHub, and follows the usual agile practices (in zenhub over GitHub).</p> <p>The process to manage changes, deal with issues and incidents is detailed in the handbook⁸³.</p> <p>We use CI in GitHub actions for unit and integration testing.</p> <p>Since there are several site deployments,</p>	<p>ReadMetrics[CMS]</p> <p>All of the development for the ReadMetrics components is open-source, all of it is on GitHub⁸⁴ where issues and requests related to the source code are handled.</p> <p>The team follows the SCRUM agile practices : daily scrums, monthly sprint and reviews, sprint retrospectives and planning.</p> <p>An online documentation for each ReadMetrics module (ezparse⁸⁵, ezmeasure⁸⁶, node-ezmeasure⁸⁷ and ezmeasure-admin⁸⁸) is provided.</p>

⁷⁵ <https://github.com/Laniakea-elixir-it>

⁷⁶ <https://github.com/Laniakea-elixir-it/laniakea-ci-infrastructure>

⁷⁷ <https://laniakea.readthedocs.io/en/latest/csa/>

⁷⁸ [https://wiki.gcube-system.org/gcube/Continuous_Integration_procedure_\(2019\)](https://wiki.gcube-system.org/gcube/Continuous_Integration_procedure_(2019))

⁷⁹ <https://code-repo.d4science.org/gCubeCI/gCubeReleases>

⁸⁰ <https://gitlab.inria.fr>

⁸¹ <https://gitlab.cc-asp.fraunhofer.de/>

⁸² <https://github.com/materials-marketplace/>

⁸³ <https://github.com/oda-hub/doc-handbook>

⁸⁴ <https://github.com/ezparse-project/>

⁸⁵ <https://github.com/ezparse-project/ezparse#readme>

⁸⁶ <https://github.com/ezparse-project/ezmeasure#readme>

⁸⁷ <https://github.com/ezparse-project/node-ezmeasure#readme>

⁸⁸ <https://github.com/ezparse-project/ezmeasure-admin#readme>

managed by different entities, CD is not in the central GitHub repository, but in GitLab/GitHub repositories of individual sites. The changes are pulled by the sites automatically, so CI/CD is fully automatic but spread between GitHub and GitLab's. Finally, there are live fuzzy integration tests which assert state of the site(s).

CI with Travis has been used for ezPAARSE⁸⁹ until it started requiring a paid subscription. There is the willingness to migrate to an alternative repository (Gitlab or Jenkins), locally hosted at Inist-CNRS.

A contact form⁹⁰ is available on the national instance of ezMESURE for centralizing all requests non related to the code.

⁸⁹ <https://ezparse-project.github.io/ezparse/>

⁹⁰ <https://ezmeasure.couperin.org/contact-us>

10. Appendix-3

In the following figure show an excerpt from the service self-assessment assessment questionnaire in collaboration with T7.4.

Service List	Service Self-Assessment Questionnaire						
	QUESTIONS CATEGORIES						
	Technology Readiness Level (TRL)	Service users		Service demand	Workplan	Functionalities	
	Q1. What is the level of the service you provide: complete & in production/not already complete but in production/prototype/development?	Q2. How many (groups of) users are using/testing the service approximately? (from EOSC-Pillar use cases/ from other communities).	Q3. What have been the target users (maybe add an approximate number of them if this info is tracked), domain (based on the past deployed instances) and if there is a different target users excepted in Pillar?	Q4. Have you already received an explicit service-demand from communities in WP6?	Q5. What is your current workplan if not in production (main steps and dates)?	Q6. Do you miss functionalities or features? What are they?	Q7. Did you receive demands for new features? Are you aware of missing features that prevent potential users to use the service you provide?
SP1-7.4.1- The use of acceleration resources (GPU, FPGA) jerome.pansanel@iphc.cnrs.fr	TRL8.	0 from EOSC-Pillar use cases / 4 from other communities.		Explicit service-demand from WP6.2 and WP6.3. WP6.5 may also be interested in a near future.	We are currently increasing our GPUs capacity to host more use-cases.		
SP2-7.4.2- Galaxy as a service platform, also named Laniakea or ReCaS service giacinto.donvito@ba.infn.it arica.antonacci@ba.infn.it ma.tangaro@ibiom.cnr.it	TRL9	Currently, several important Italian Institutions are using Laniakea for their daily work: Istituto Ortopedico Rizzoli (2 internal Galaxy servers), Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale della Puglia e della Basilicata (2 internal Galaxy servers and 1 IRIDA instance), Ospedale Pediatrico Giannina Gaslini (public server), University of Milan (2 public servers).	Laniakea aims to provide Galaxy to end users ranging from small research groups to institutions or SMEs, on suitable computation resources, removing the need to maintain their own hardware and software infrastructure, making Galaxy also available for those who don't have IT expertise.	Of course the service is strictly related to Task 6.6. Outside of this use case we didn't received demand	The service is already in production. Nevertheless we are working to improve the backend, in particular the service maintenance over time, and adding new features (like different applications on-demand). We plan a major update release of Laniakea, including the progress developed in the context of EOSC-Pillar, for the first	Being the service already in production, it is not missing any feature needed for its functioning. Additional functionalities are in development.	No, apart from the ones we already planned (including new data services, and exploiting data aware scheduling using this new data services).
SP3-7.4.3-Virtual Laboratories/Virtual Research Environments supporting collaboration and co-operation among scientists leonardo.candela@isti.cnr.it	VREs are TRL9 because they are really used in production settings by real communities ... all of this is independent from EOSC-Pillar.	D4Science operates more than 150 VREs by 19 gateways overall serving more than 13,000 users. One of these gateway is the one set up for EOSC-Pillar and available at https://eosc-pillar.d4science.org	The EOSC-Pillar gateway is serving a total of 438 users ... the large majority of users comes from pre-existing VREs (namely 136 users from the Alien and Invasive Species, 253 users from the AnalyticsLab). In total this Gateway is currently offering 6 VREs ... 4 of them stem explicitly from EOSC-Pillar ...	Not really, I hope they will come soon! Some use cases are interested yet no real request has been raised. Some examples: * Use case 6.2 might be interested in setting up a VRE; * Use case 6.3 might be interested in setting up a VRE; * The new COVID use case will likely lead to a VRE based on	Once we receive a request for a new VRE, we can set it up in a very short time frame (hours / days) depending from the services to be provided. Once the VRE is up and running its development is expected to continue with the contribution from the community, e.g. the		